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Sustainable Management Strategies for Long-Term Adaptation in the Evolving Work Reality from Crisis to Organizational Resilience

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Abstract: *This study analyzes the managerial impact and challenges generated by the COVID-19 pandemic on the organizational environment, with a specific focus on “the renowned international company operating on the Romanian market” (The Company). The research examines the influence of teleworking, organizational culture changes, and crisis management strategies on employee performance and well-being. Data were collected through a questionnaire applied to a sample of 72 employees and statistically analyzed. The results show a significant increase in work schedule flexibility and productivity during and after the pandemic, supporting the long-term adoption of hybrid work models. Communication and collaboration were negatively affected during the pandemic but later recovered through the implementation of digital solutions and adaptive leadership measures. Although stress levels slightly increased in the post-pandemic period, job satisfaction and employee commitment reached higher levels than before the pandemic. The study highlights the essential role of effective management in enhancing employee adaptability and strengthening organizational resilience. The conclusions emphasize the need for sustainable strategies that include work flexibility, employee support, and ongoing digitalization as key factors for long-term performance and development in an unpredictable organizational environment.*

Keywords: *organizational adaptability; effective management; teleworking; flexibility; job satisfaction*

1. Introduction

Consulting the specialized literature, we synthesized representative approaches that highlight the profound impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the international organizational environment from the perspective of sustainable management, emphasizing the need for adaptation, resilience, and innovation. Changes in work structure, such as adopting telework and digital transformation, have been essential in ensuring operational continuity. Significant financial and operational challenges, including supply chain disruptions and financial pressure, have necessitated strategic reevaluation and the implementation of innovative management solutions adapted to environmental uncertainty.

The pandemic has significantly reshaped the global organizational environment, generating an urgent need for adaptation, resilience, and sustainable management strategies. This study aims to investigate the impact of teleworking, organizational culture changes, and crisis management strategies on employee performance and well-being within a multinational enterprise operating in Romania. The core objective is to understand how these transformations influenced employee adaptability, productivity, satisfaction, and stress levels, as well as how effective management contributed to organizational resilience.

To achieve this goal, we employed quantitative research design based on a structured questionnaire. The instrument was inspired by the EURES “COVID-19 Returning to Work Survey” and adapted to suit the specific objectives of this study. The questionnaire was distributed online to ensure accessibility and anonymity, and responses were collected on a 10-point Likert scale. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS to identify trends, correlations, and significant differences across three key timeframes: pre-pandemic, during the pandemic, and post-pandemic.

The sample consisted of 72 employees from *The Company*, including a balanced gender distribution and diverse roles across departments such as IT, SAP consulting, HR, and Business Solutions. This company was selected due to its international scope, digital infrastructure, and rapid adaptation to pandemic constraints, making it representative of globally integrated organizations undergoing systemic change.

The results revealed a substantial increase in work schedule flexibility and perceived productivity during and after the pandemic, particularly among employees working in hybrid or remote arrangements. Communication and collaboration experienced a temporary decline during the crisis but were later restored through digital platforms and managerial initiatives. Employee satisfaction improved slightly post-pandemic, while stress levels showed a moderate increase, likely linked to the long-term effects of change and uncertainty. Adaptability and commitment also rebounded, especially in connection with effective leadership and support systems.

This research contributes to the literature by offering empirical evidence on how sustainable management practices, rooted in flexibility and innovation, can buffer the effects of systemic crises and enhance organizational resilience. Moreover, the study emphasizes the central role of managerial responsiveness in supporting employee well-being and performance during turbulent periods.

The structure of this paper is as follows: the first section presents the theoretical framework and literature review; the second outlines the research methodology; the third provides an in-depth analysis of the empirical results; and the final section discusses the implications, limitations, and future directions for sustainable management practices in the post-crisis work environment.

2. Literature Review

According to the approaches described by Ali et al. (2023), Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Raj et al. (2022), Corte et al. (2022), Ma & Zhang (2022), Waal et al. (2021), Hamsal & Ichsan (2021), and Chowdhury et al. (2021), the COVID-19 pandemic challenge included the need to adapt to remote work and digital transformation, maintain organizational resilience, address financial and operational difficulties, manage changes in organizational culture and communication, and navigate the uncertainties of the global economic landscape.

During this period, large populations were affected. Waal et al. (2021), Chowdhury et al. (2021), and Hamsal & Ichsan (2021) suggest that the pandemic generated devastating effects on public health, the economy, and society, causing major disruptions and imposing the need for coordinated actions at local, national, and international levels. This highlighted the vulnerability of organizational structures to external shocks, requiring a rapid and often unprecedented response from management teams.

Thus, the scale and magnitude of the pandemic prompted a reevaluation of traditional management practices, pushing organizations to urgently adapt. This need for adaptation underscores the importance of revising and adjusting management methods, as management, by its nature, involves the coordination and control of organizational activities. In times of crisis, the role of management expands, and under conditions of uncertainty, decisive decision-making under pressure must ensure both the continuity, resilience, and long-term sustainability of the organization. Management involves planning, organizing, leading, and controlling resources to achieve specific objectives (Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Raj et al., 2022; Yustian, 2021).

Effective management during a crisis requires a delicate balance between short-term responses and long-term strategic planning, with a strong emphasis on adaptability, employee well-being, and ethical considerations. Crisis management theories (Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Raj et al., 2022; Dwivedi et al., 2020) provide frameworks and principles for understanding and responding to

challenges during times of uncertainty and disruption. According to Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Al Mazrouei (2023), and Hamsal & Ichsan (2021), the pandemic had a profound impact on the organizational environment, redefining how organizations operate, communicate, and manage their workforce.

The pressure to make timely decisions is amplified during a crisis. Managers have the responsibility to protect the health and safety of their employees while trying to maintain operational viability. This dual responsibility requires a balance between the urgent need for action and the strategic foresight to anticipate the long-term implications of these decisions (Al Mazrouei, 2023; Raj et al., 2022; Hamsal & Ichsan, 2021; Bailey & Breslin, 2021). According to Krishnan et al. (2022), effective crisis management often involves taking preventive measures to mitigate risks, as well as being prepared to implement contingency plans quickly when initial plans fail.

In response to the global pandemic, management practices had to undergo rapid adaptation. Leaders and managers were tasked with guiding organizations through an environment characterized by uncertainty and continuous change. This involved making difficult short-term decisions, reevaluating priorities, and continuously adapting strategies based on evolving circumstances (Hamsal & Ichsan, 2021; Bailey & Breslin, 2021; Dwivedi et al., 2020; Conger, 2020; Nembhard Ingrid et al., 2020). Additionally, the crisis highlighted the importance of ethical management practices (Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Hamsal & Ichsan, 2021; Raj et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2020) and the need to prioritize employee well-being, including support for mental health (Aldianto et al., 2021; Begun & Jiang, 2020).

International organizations played a significant role in the global pandemic response, facing unprecedented challenges that evaluated their ability to adapt and respond effectively across borders. One of the main challenges for international organizations during the pandemic was coordinating a cohesive response among various countries. This required a delicate balance between developing global strategies that could be universally applied and adapting responses to fit the specific needs and circumstances of each country (Dwivedi et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2020; Chen, 2020). The pandemic also highlighted the fragility of global supply chains. International organizations had to manage significant disruptions due to lockdowns, border closures, and shifts in demand. This situation required agile supply chain strategies and innovative solutions to maintain the flow of essential goods and services, from medical supplies to food and other critical commodities (Kumar et al., 2020; Chen, 2020).

In conclusion, according to the approaches described by Raj et al. (2022), Hamsal & Ichsan (2021), Lozano & Barreiro-Gen (2021), and Bailey & Breslin (2021), the role of management in international organizations during a pandemic goes beyond traditional responsibilities, requiring a comprehensive and adaptive leadership approach.

3. Theoretical Mechanism

One of the key challenges faced by international organizations during the pandemic was the need for effective communication and coordination among different countries with varying resources and regulatory environments. These organizations had to manage the complexity of the global crisis, including cross-border coordination efforts and adapting strategies to the specific needs and circumstances of each country. International organizations not only had to rapidly adapt their operations and strategies, but also had to manage the political, economic, and social implications of the pandemic, which further complicated their ability to coordinate and respond effectively.

Operating under conditions of uncertainty, making decisions under pressure, ensuring organizational continuity and resilience, balancing short-term responses with long-term planning, and prioritizing adaptability, employee well-being, and ethical considerations - management can guide organizations through the turbulent waters of a crisis toward recovery and eventual growth.

3.1 Changes in Work Structure: Teleworking and the Development of Organizational Resilience

The COVID-19 pandemic imposed significant changes in the work structure of organizations, with teleworking becoming the primary mode of operation. To ensure business continuity and enable remote work during the pandemic, organizations were forced to quickly adopt technology and embrace digital transformation, a process detailed in the works of Vu (2023), Raj et al. (2022), Santos-Pereira et al. (2022), and Dwivedi et al. (2020).

According to the approaches described by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Baker (2022), Dwivedi et al. (2020), and Minciu et al. (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic created unprecedented challenges for international organizations regarding coordination, supply chain management, and communication across various countries, highlighting the importance of effective coordination and communication for international organizations.

This brought about a seismic shift in the global work environment, pushing teleworking from a niche or occasional arrangement to an essential and widespread practice (Erđiaw-Kwasie et al., 2023; Afridi et al., 2023; Ameen et al., 2023). This transformation was primarily driven by government-imposed lockdowns and social distancing measures aimed at controlling the spread of the virus. Organizations worldwide had to rapidly adapt to remote work setups to protect employee health and ensure operational continuity. This necessary but rapid pivot introduced a range of challenges and fundamentally altered the nature of work (Wang et al., 2024; Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2020).

The rapid adoption of various digital technologies was essential for transitioning to a remote work environment, as emphasized in research by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Aleem et al. (2023), and He & Harris (2020). According to Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), cloud computing services played a crucial role in providing the flexibility and scalability organizations needed to support remote work, becoming the backbone of these organizations by enabling access to data and applications from anywhere, thus allowing seamless work processes outside the traditional office environment.

Similarly, Raj et al. (2022) highlights the importance of collaborative tools and platforms such as Slack, Microsoft Teams, and Asana, which revolutionized how teams communicate and manage projects by offering functionalities like chat, video conferencing, and real-time document collaboration - essential for overcoming physical barriers between remote employees. Additionally, Dwivedi et al. (2020) emphasize the vital role of video conferencing platforms such as Zoom and Google Meet in maintaining social connections and a sense of community through meetings, webinars, and social interactions, even in the absence of direct physical contact.

The transition to teleworking introduced significant challenges for various organizations, initially facing technological obstacles such as ensuring reliable internet access for all staff and establishing secure connections for remote use of corporate systems, as highlighted by Ameen et al. (2023). Moreover, they point out that the need for advanced cybersecurity measures became imperative considering the shift to remote work, increasing the potential attack surface exposed to cyber threats. In this context, international organizations had to strengthen their IT security to protect sensitive data and communications, adopting advanced encryption, multi-factor authentication, and secure access protocols to mitigate the risk of cyber threats in a distributed work environment (Reuschl et al., 2022).

The pandemic forcefully accelerated the adoption of teleworking, acting as a catalyst for profound digital transformation within organizations - a process that goes beyond merely adopting new technologies to include a fundamental shift in organizational culture, with a focus on flexibility, digital literacy, and adaptability, as highlighted by Dwivedi et al. (2020). Furthermore, teleworking brought about a profound change in the spatial and temporal dimensions of work, making the physical office - which once was the center of daily work activities - less relevant and prompting a reevaluation of the necessity and use of office space. At the same time, the rigid adherence to a 9-to-5 workday became more flexible, according to Ameen et al. (2023).

Many organizations adopted asynchronous work models, allowing employees to adjust their work hours around other responsibilities such as caregiving or homeschooling, which became particularly relevant

during the pandemic. This situation highlighted the need for organizations to establish clear remote work policies that define expectations for availability, communication, and working hours to prevent burnout and support employee well-being. The context created by the pandemic required organizations to make significant adjustments to their work structures to develop the necessary resilience in the face of uncertainties, as emphasized by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023) and Savira (2021).

The unprecedented challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic underscored the importance of organizational resilience as a strategic priority, an observation supported by research conducted by Gomes et al. (2023), Ali et al. (2023), and Ma & Zhang (2022). In this context, resilience involves the organization's ability to withstand shocks, adapt to new realities, and emerge not just unaffected, but stronger and more adaptable - a viewpoint supported by He & Harris (2020). The journey toward achieving such resilience is complex and involves flexibility, employee support, innovation, and strategic foresight, according to studies by Napier et al. (2024), Grego et al. (2024), and Mena et al. (2022).

At the core of organizational resilience lie flexibility and adaptability - qualities that enable businesses to navigate the uncertainties of a crisis. Flexibility in work arrangements, such as adopting teleworking, proved essential in maintaining operations while protecting employee health (Ameen et al., 2023; Chudziński et al., 2023). This adaptability extends to organizational processes and programs, requiring a shift away from rigid structures toward more fluid and responsive operational models.

Crises function as catalysts for innovation, forcing organizations to identify new ways to deliver products and services. Resilient organizations, as described by Gomes et al. (2023) and Ali et al. (2023), seize these moments to drive innovation by adopting a mindset focused on continuous learning and development. This initiative-taking approach, centered on seeking new skills, technologies, and processes, allows organizations to respond agilely to changes and discover opportunities even in times of adversity, as highlighted by Hamsal & Ichsan (2021) and Bailey & Breslin (2021). The pandemic demonstrated that the capacity for innovation is not just about technology but also about organizational agility and the ability to reimagine business models and practices.

Building organizational resilience in the face of a pandemic or any crisis involves a comprehensive strategy that embraces flexibility, supports employees, fosters innovation, and incorporates strategic foresight into planning and risk management. Organizations that successfully navigated the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated that resilience is not just about survival but about thriving in uncertainty - using adversity as an opportunity for growth and transformation. The lessons learned during this period will undoubtedly shape the future of organizational development, emphasizing the importance of resilience in an ever-changing global landscape.

3.2 The Impact of the Pandemic on Organizational Culture and Communication

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on organizational culture and communication highlighted the importance of leadership and change management as top priorities within organizations, as noted by Aleem et al. (2023) and He & Harris (2020). This period of unprecedented change not only evaluated the resilience and adaptability of organizations but, according to the study by Daum & Maraist (2021), also emphasized the need for effective leadership in navigating all challenges, leading to a profound reevaluation of organizational culture. This culture extends beyond operational aspects to the very foundation of organizations - their values, beliefs, and practices. In this context, leaders are more than ever faced with the challenge of maintaining a united and cohesive culture in a work environment disconnected from the physical workplace, as highlighted by Afridi et al. (2023) and Damayanti et al. (2023).

The pandemic amplified the imperative for leaders to combine strategic and sustainable management with a deep connection to the human experience of their teams, demonstrating that leadership is essential in times of crisis. In this context, leaders adapted their leadership styles to effectively address the challenges brought by the pandemic, a perspective supported by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Al Mazrouei (2023), and Santoso et al. (2022).

According to Zoonen et al. (2021) and Azizi et al. (2021), it is imperative for leaders to maintain clear and transparent communication by providing employees with accurate information and specific

guidance. Furthermore, Bieńkowska et al. (2023) emphasize the need to cultivate a culture of open communication, creating an environment where employees feel comfortable expressing their concerns and ideas. This agile approach was essential not only for effectively navigating the crisis but also for leveraging emerging opportunities, demonstrating how flexibility and responsiveness form the foundation of organizational resilience, as highlighted by Nguyen et al. (2022).

The dissolution of the traditional office space as the epicenter of work interactions underscored the importance of fostering an organizational culture grounded in trust and accountability, as emphasized by Chaubey & Sahoo (2021). In this new paradigm, leaders must express trust in employees' ability to fulfill their responsibilities autonomously, marking a significant shift from traditional supervisory practices, such as micromanagement, toward results-oriented management, as shown by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023). This focus on outcomes rather than strict processes suggests a deep trust in employees' professional ethics and abilities, fostering a sense of belonging and individual accountability for organizational achievements, according to Nguyen et al. (2022).

The pandemic heightened the need for effective change management, as highlighted by Raj et al. (2022) and Waal et al. (2021). In this context, leaders, according to Bieńkowska et al. (2023), must be prepared to guide their organizations through rapid and unpredictable changes. This involves making swift decisions and adapting strategies to enable international organizations to respond agilely to changing circumstances - essential for their survival and prosperity. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic generated significant disruptions in the organizational environment, as noted by Durst et al. (2024), causing decreases in employee motivation and wages, a reduction in customers and sales, additional costs associated with hiring new employees, work interruptions caused by employee infections, and increased workloads - issues also discussed by Aleem et al. (2023), He & Harris (2020), and Raj et al. (2022). As a result, international organizations were forced to make tough decisions regarding layoffs, temporary suspensions, and salary cuts to maintain financial stability.

The increased importance of empathy and understanding emerged as one of the most profound shifts in leadership dynamics during the pandemic. Recognizing the human element of the crisis - acknowledging the fears, anxieties, and challenges faced by employees - became a central aspect of effective leadership (Al Mazrouei, 2023; Santoso et al., 2022; Raina, 2022). Leaders who show empathy toward their employees' circumstances cultivate a supportive and inclusive culture that values well-being alongside productivity. This empathetic approach encourages open communication, strengthens team bonds, and builds a sense of community and belonging that are essential for maintaining morale and engagement during challenging times.

Adapting to a remote work environment imposed by the pandemic required a significant paradigm shift in organizational culture, which now places greater emphasis on innovation, collaboration, and continuous learning to facilitate adaptation to change. This transition is well-documented by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Dwivedi et al. (2020), and Li et al. (2021). In this context, effective communication became a critical element in managing change, with leaders such as those mentioned by Chaubey & Sahoo (2021) needing to clearly communicate the reasons for change, set clear expectations, and provide regular updates to keep employees well-informed and engaged. Transparency in communication, essential for building trust and ensuring that employees feel valued and understood, is a key point emphasized by Bieńkowska et al. (2023) and Nguyen et al. (2022). This involved not only adopting appropriate technologies but also adjusting communication styles to become more empathetic and inclusive, considering the diverse challenges faced by employees during the pandemic.

Adapting leadership styles to effectively lead remote teams and maintain employee engagement and motivation was an essential requirement in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Damayanti et al., 2023; Cremers & Curşeu, 2023). This adaptation involved not only changes in communication methods but also in the strategic and emotional approaches adopted by leaders to manage geographically dispersed teams.

Leaders who managed to adapt and adopt a more flexible, empathetic, and goal-oriented leadership style were the ones who most effectively maintained team engagement and motivation in the remote work context imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. This adaptability not only ensured operational continuity but also laid the foundation for a more resilient and adaptable work environment in the future.

3.3 Financial and Operational Challenges

The COVID-19 pandemic generated significant financial and operational challenges for organizations worldwide, putting pressure on their sustainability, efficiency, and growth prospects, as documented by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023), Howe et al. (2021), and Lu (2021). In international organizations across various sectors, financial stability was seriously affected by sudden drops in revenue and significant constraints on cash flow, representing unprecedented challenges. The adoption of lockdown restrictions and social distancing measures, although essential to limiting the spread of COVID-19, resulted in a dramatic decrease in consumer spending, as noted by Aleem et al. (2023), and led to the near-complete shutdown of physical business operations, as reported by He & Harris (2020).

The declines caused by the pandemic were not only operational challenges but also significantly impacted on the financial structures of international organizations, drastically reducing revenues and placing enormous pressure on the sustainability of operations, according to Howe et al. (2021) and Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023). In the absence of normal cash flow, organizations faced difficulties in managing operational costs such as rent, utilities, salaries, and payments to suppliers, a situation detailed by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023) and Nguyen et al. (2023). For small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) particularly this created a severe liquidity crisis. The lack of cash flow not only endangered daily operations but also limited businesses' ability to invest in the adjustments or innovations needed to adapt to a constantly changing environment.

To manage the pandemic-induced economic downturn, which caused revenue losses and rising costs, organizations had to adopt effective strategies, as stated by Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber (2023) and Moosavi et al. (2022). Disruptions in supply chains, which caused labor and material shortages as well as supply inconsistencies, had a significant impact on global supply chains, creating unprecedented disruptions and difficulties for manufacturing organizations, particularly in emerging economies. This situation required innovative approaches, as suggested by Kumar et al. (2020) and Chen (2020), including the adoption of modern technologies and the implementation of contingency plans to mitigate the negative impacts on organizational financial and operational performance, a perspective shared by Howe et al. (2021).

Access to capital became even more difficult in the context of the pandemic, with traditional sources of financing becoming cautious in the face of economic uncertainty, as highlighted by Howe et al. (2021). This caution led to tighter lending conditions, complicating businesses' ability to obtain loans or other forms of financial support, a situation confirmed by Nguyen et al. (2023) and Erdiaw-Kwasie et al. (2023). This left many organizations facing tough decisions, including layoffs, scaling back operations, or, in the worst cases, permanent closures. These challenges required rapid adaptation strategies, evaluating the resilience and flexibility of organizations worldwide.

Financial institutions, facing the risks associated with the uncertain economic climate, adopted more conservative lending practices (Moser-Plautz & Schmidhuber, 2023; Nguyen et al., 2023). Banks and lenders increased scrutiny of loan applications, demanding stricter evidence of business viability and solvency. This shift resulted in greater barriers to obtaining traditional loans, credit lines, and other forms of debt financing. The tightened credit conditions were a result of lenders' efforts to mitigate their own risk exposure in an environment where many businesses faced reduced revenues and uncertain futures. As a result, even businesses that had been financially stable before the pandemic faced difficulties obtaining loans or were forced to accept less favorable terms. This situation affected their ability to sustain current operations or invest in adaptation strategies, a reality highlighted by Raj et al. (2022), Pavlatos & Kostakis (2022), and Belás et al. (2021).

Increased costs associated with implementing health and safety measures, adapting workspaces for social distancing, and investing in technology for remote work presented substantial financial challenges for organizations, particularly SMEs. According to Howe et al. (2021) and Achim et al. (2021), the unexpected expenses generated in this context further intensified the financial pressure already heightened by the broader economic impact of the pandemic, emphasizing the essential importance of rigorous financial planning and management. As businesses attempted to navigate these difficulties, accessing government support and seeking cost-effective solutions for health, safety, and technology became essential for financial stability and long-term resilience.

In response to these challenges, international organizations implemented a variety of strategies to secure the necessary capital, as supported by the research of Nguyen et al. (2023), Howe et al. (2021), and Lu (2021):

- **Exploring Alternative Financing:** Companies looked beyond traditional bank loans and equity investments, exploring alternative financing options such as crowdfunding, revenue-based financing, and fintech solutions. These alternatives often offer more flexible terms and are accessible to a wider range of businesses.
- **Government Support Programs:** Many governments worldwide introduced support programs to ease the financial pressure on businesses. These programs, including loan guarantees, grants, and tax relief measures, provided a crucial lifeline for organizations struggling to access other forms of capital.
- **Strengthening Financial Management:** The challenges of accessing capital underscored the importance of robust financial management. Businesses focused on improving cash flow management, reducing non-essential expenses, and strengthening their financial positions to enhance their attractiveness to investors and lenders.
- **The COVID-19 pandemic brought unprecedented financial and operational challenges to organizations, prompting a reevaluation of business strategies and requiring rapid adaptations to cope with a changing economic landscape. The profound impact on supply chains, the need for accelerated digital transformation, and the adaptation to new health and safety regulations evaluated organizations' resilience and flexibility. In this context, the importance of solid financial management, innovation, and government support became evident, highlighting the need for organizations to be prepared to navigate uncertainties and ensure a stable foundation for future growth.**

4 Methodology

4.1 Purpose, Objectives, Hypotheses, Variables

Companies worldwide were forced to adapt to a new economic and operational reality during the COVID-19 pandemic, which transformed the traditional way of working. In this context, companies faced unprecedented financial and operational challenges, including supply chain disruptions, the need for rapid digital transformation, and adaptation to new health and safety regulations.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of teleworking, organizational culture changes, and crisis management strategies on the performance and well-being of employees at the company. This study aims to analyze how these elements have influenced the work environment, and the changes implemented within The Company. Evaluating these aspects is essential for understanding how international companies can overcome crises and improve management strategies to support both economic growth and employee well-being at The Company. Thus, the proposed purpose focuses on the concrete impact of the pandemic on the work environment and the changes made within organizations.

Research Objectives

- **Objective 1:** To assess the impact of the pandemic on work schedule flexibility and how this has influenced employee productivity at The Company.
- **Objective 2:** To analyze the effects of the pandemic on communication and collaboration within teams.
- **Objective 3:** To investigate the effects of the pandemic on professional satisfaction and stress levels among employees at The Company.
- **Objective 4:** To evaluate the correlation between employee adaptability at The Company and the effectiveness of management during the global health crisis.

The proposed objectives are interconnected and complementary, each addressing various aspects of the pandemic's impact on The Company's work environment.

- O1 focuses on investigating how the pandemic affected work schedule flexibility and how this change influenced employee productivity.
- O2 addresses how the pandemic impacted team communication and collaboration, aiming to identify challenges or barriers that emerged due to pandemic restrictions.
- O3 explores how the pandemic influenced job satisfaction and stress levels, seeking to understand the effects of remote work and economic uncertainty on employee perceptions of their work experience.
- O4 investigates how the pandemic influenced employee engagement and adaptability, aiming to understand the relationship between these aspects and the effectiveness of management in handling human resources and organizational challenges during the crisis. The study aims to assess how employees' capacity to adapt to the changes imposed by the pandemic influences the management of human resources and organizational issues within the company.

Research Hypotheses

- Hypothesis 1.1 (O1): Work schedule flexibility increased significantly during the pandemic due to the necessity of adopting remote work models. *The increased flexibility of the work schedule had a positive impact on employee productivity at The Company.*
- Hypothesis 1.2 (O1): The implementation of a flexible work schedule during the pandemic led to an increase in employee productivity at The Company.
- Hypothesis 2.1 (O2): The pandemic improved/deteriorated communication and collaboration within teams at The Company due to the rapid adoption of digital technologies and online collaboration tools.
- Hypothesis 3.1 (O3): Employee stress levels were significantly higher during the pandemic compared to pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods.
- Hypothesis 4.1 (O4): Employee engagement decreased during the pandemic due to economic uncertainties and personal pressures.
- Hypothesis 4.2 (O4): Employee engagement and adaptability at The Company increased during the global health crisis, and this increase is directly correlated with the effectiveness of management, which implemented appropriate support strategies and effective communication.

Variables of the Study. For the current study, based on the previously stated purpose, objectives, and hypotheses, the research variables can be structured as follows:

Demographic Variables:

- Age (employees' age in years) – reflects demographic diversity and may influence perspectives and behaviors related to work in the pandemic context.
- Gender (male / female) – may reveal differences in experiences and responses to organizational policies based on gender.
- City – provides geographical context, potentially influencing access to resources, work culture, and the direct impact of the pandemic.
- Department
- Tenure in the Company (number of years) – reflects employee experience and loyalty to the company, which may affect engagement and perspectives on organizational changes.
- Type of Work (office-based / hybrid / telework) – indicates adaptability to new work models imposed by the pandemic, affecting productivity, stress, and job satisfaction; the work environment will be evaluated based on the three studied periods.

Independent Variables:

O1: Evaluating the impact of the pandemic on work schedule flexibility and its influence on employee productivity at The Company:

- Degree of work schedule flexibility (e.g., flexible hours, working from home)
- Access to digital resources and technologies for remote work
- Managerial support for flexible work arrangements

O2: Analyzing the effects of the pandemic on team communication and collaboration:

- Use of digital communication technologies (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams)
- Frequency and quality of team communication
- Collaboration policies implemented by the company.
- Number of virtual meetings and collaboration sessions

O3: Investigating the effects of the pandemic on job satisfaction and stress levels among The Company employees:

- Workload and required overtime
- Access to resources for working from home (e.g., equipment, workspace)
- Support provided for mental and physical health (e.g., counseling, wellness programs)
- Job stability and economic uncertainty
- Work-life balance

O4: Evaluating the correlation between employee adaptability at The Company and management effectiveness during the global health crisis:

- Management strategies implemented during the crisis (e.g., business continuity plans, effective communication)
- Level of managerial support perceived by employees
- Adaptability measures implemented (e.g., training, additional resources)
- Frequency and quality of managerial feedback

Possible Dependent Variables:

Overall Purpose: Employee performance and well-being

- O1: Employee productivity
- O2: Quality of team communication
 - Effectiveness of employee collaboration
- O3: Employee job satisfaction
 - Employee stress levels
- O4: Employee adaptability
 - Management effectiveness
- O5: Employee engagement
 - Employees' capacity to adapt

These variables are designed to collect relevant data that will allow evaluation of the hypotheses formulated in this study and to provide a detailed picture of the pandemic's influence on the work environment at The Company.

This research offers valuable insights into The Company's capacity for adaptation and organizational resilience in the face of significant change during a crisis, highlighting the importance of effective human and operational resource management from a sustainable management perspective.

4.2 Sampling

The research was conducted between November 15, 2023, and June 1, 2024, with the approval of The Company representatives for employee participation in the study.

The sample size for this study consists of 72 employees of the company, including 35 women and 37 men, who were affected by the implementation of remote work and organizational changes during and after the pandemic. These participants hold junior, mid-level, and senior positions.

According to Fornell & Cha (1994), this sample size is sufficient to conduct a consistent analysis. The percentage of female respondents is 48.6%, while the percentage of male respondents is 51.4%. The average age of respondents is 35 years.

Given these challenges, the study sets clear objectives: to evaluate the effect of teleworking on employee productivity and well-being, to investigate their level of job satisfaction, and to analyze the effectiveness of team communication and collaboration under these unusual conditions.

4.3 Research Methods and Instruments

Quantitative research was appropriate for this exploratory study, which aimed to analyze how teleworking, organizational culture changes, and crisis management strategies have affected employee performance and well-being at the international company The Company.

The research method used was the survey method, an interactive method that involves direct information exchange between the researcher and the subjects under investigation, with the purpose of collecting data on certain phenomena, situations, or behaviors. The relationship between the participants in the survey is dual but asymmetric, as "the researcher designs, formulates, and asks a series of questions, encouraging the investigated subjects to respond" (Bocoş, M., 2017, p. 47).

The specific instrument of this method is the questionnaire, a structured plan of written, successive questions based on methodological, logical, and psychological considerations (Chelcea, S., 2004, p. 105; Bocoş, M., 2017, p. 48). By completing the questionnaire, a set of responses is collected regarding the investigated situation, which the researcher does not directly observe, as these are manifestations occurring over a certain period and within a certain context. The questionnaire follows a circular process, moving through the stages of general problem – specific objective – formulation of questions – administration – data coding – analysis – general problem, and so on (Palade, M.R., 2014, p. 48).

Based on the identified variables and to evaluate the proposed hypotheses, the questionnaire used for data collection includes structured and semi-structured questions, providing measurable responses that were statistically analyzed. The research method employed in this study was inspired by a questionnaire published on the official website of EURES (European Job Mobility Portal), accessed on August 24, 2021 (https://eures.europa.eu/five-key-questions-your-covid-19-returning-work-survey-2021-08-24_ro). The referenced questionnaire, titled "*Five Key Questions for Your COVID-19 Returning to Work Survey*," served as a guide for developing the questionnaire used in this research. The questions were adapted and customized to align with the specific objectives of the study.

The questionnaire consists of four sections:

- The first section includes five questions, both structured and open-ended.
- The next three sections each include nine structured questions, totaling 32 questions.

To collect responses, a 10-point Likert scale was used, where 1 represents "strongly disagree" or "very dissatisfied," and 10 represents "strongly agree" or "very satisfied."

Questionnaire Structure:

- The first section focuses on collecting demographic data, such as age, city of residence, department, tenure in the company, and gender. This information helps to better understand participant profiles and analyze differences in work experiences based on demographic characteristics.
- The second, third, and fourth sections are designed to evaluate participants' work experiences in three distinct contexts: pre-pandemic, during the pandemic, and post-pandemic. In each section, participants were asked to evaluate the same aspects of their work environment using the same 1-to-10 scale to facilitate result comparison. These aspects include:
 - Work schedule flexibility
 - Productivity level
 - Effectiveness of communication and collaboration
 - Job satisfaction
 - Stress levels
 - Commitment to the company
 - Adaptability to organizational changes
 - Management effectiveness in addressing issues.

Using identical questions across all sections allows for a comparative analysis of responses in different time frames, contributing to the identification of key trends and challenges faced by the workforce during the pandemic.

Data were collected via an online questionnaire (Google Forms) created for this study. To ensure confidentiality and encourage honest responses, participants (The Company employees) completed the questionnaire anonymously.

The data collected in this study are both quantitative and qualitative:

- Quantitative data comes from closed-ended questions with multiple-choice and Likert scale responses, enabling standardized measurement of satisfaction levels, productivity, and other variables.
- Qualitative data comes from open-ended responses, allowing participants to freely express their personal experiences and perceptions.

For analysis, the data collected were entered into a database. Numerical coding was applied to quantitative responses to facilitate statistical processing. Qualitative data were transcribed and subjected to content analysis to identify common themes and patterns.

Quantitative data analysis was conducted using SPSS statistical software. This mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data, provides a comprehensive view of the pandemic's impact on The Company employees, enabling both measurable insights and a deeper understanding of employees' subjective experiences. Through this analysis, the study aims to generate valid conclusions that directly contribute to the achievement of the research objectives.

5 Data Analysis and Results

The study included a sample of 72 participants, aged between 25 and 47 years. The mean age of the respondents was approximately 35 years, with a standard deviation of 6 years, indicating a uniform distribution of ages around the mean, with a median age also of 35 years (Table 1).

Regarding tenure in the company, this varied significantly, ranging from a minimum of 2 years to a maximum of 23 years, with a mean tenure of approximately 8 years and a standard deviation of 4 years. The work experience median was 6.5 years.

Table 1. Distribution of the Sample

Sample: 72 pers.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	SD	Median

Age	25	47	35,13	6,03	35
Work experience	2	23	8,16	4,04	6,5

The gender distribution was balanced, with 37 women (51.4%) and 35 men (48.6%) (Figure 1), reflecting a diverse and equitable participation in the study.

Figure 1. Gender Distribution

Most participants work from Cluj-Napoca, representing 51.4% of the total sample, with 37 individuals. The next largest group is from Sibiu, with 20 respondents, counting - 27.8% of the sample (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution by City

The departmental distribution of participants shows that most employees come from the IT department (29.2%, n=21) and the SAP department (25%, n=18), reflecting a significant representation of technical staff in the study (Table 3). The Human Resources and Business Solutions and Consultancy departments accounted for 15.3% (n=11) and 6.9% (n=5) of the sample, respectively, indicating diversity in the participants' organizational roles. Other departments, such as Project Management Office, Marketing, Legal, Finance, and Innovation, had lower participation, each representing less than 6% of the total (Figure 3).

The predominance of employees from the IT and SAP departments suggests that the study's structure is strongly represented by technical personnel, which may influence perceptions on certain variables such as work schedule flexibility and adaptability to remote work. The notable participation from the Human Resources and Business Solutions and Consultancy departments highlights the diversity of roles and experiences, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of the pandemic's effects on distinct functions within the company.

Figure 3. Distribution by Departments

Q1 – Work Arrangement

Before the pandemic, most respondents, 88.9% (n=64), worked on-site at the office, indicating the prevalence of the traditional work environment. A smaller percentage, 8.3% (n=6), had already adopted a hybrid work model, combining office work with remote work. Only 2.8% (n=2) of respondents worked exclusively from home (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Work Type during Time Period

During the pandemic, most respondents in the 72-person sample worked remotely from home, with 91.7% (n=66) reporting full remote work. Only a small percentage, 4.2% (n=3), worked in a hybrid model, and another 4.2% (n=3) continued to work exclusively from the office.

After the pandemic, most respondents, 61.1% (n=44), adopted a hybrid work model, combining office and remote work, indicating a preference for flexibility and adaptation to the new working conditions. A significant 23.6% (n=17) returned to working exclusively on-site. At the same time, 15.3% (n=11) of respondents continued to work fully remote (home office), showing that remote work remains a viable option even post-pandemic.

Q2 – Work Schedule Flexibility

Respondents evaluated the flexibility of their work schedule using a Likert scale from 1 to 10. A score of 5, indicating a moderate level of flexibility, was the most frequently selected, chosen by 29.2% (n=21) of participants. Scores 4 and 6 followed in frequency, with 23.6% (n=17) and 16.7% (n=12) of respondents selecting these options, respectively. 13.9% (n=10) rated flexibility as 3, suggesting a low, but not minimal, level of flexibility.

During the pandemic, the flexibility of the work schedule was evaluated significantly more positively by respondents. A score of 9, indicating an elevated level of flexibility, was the most frequently chosen, with 43.1% (n=31) of participants selecting this option. The maximum score of 10, reflecting extremely high flexibility, was chosen by 26.4% (n=19). Other high scores, such as 8 and 7, were also common, selected by 20.8% (n=15) and 8.3% (n=6) of respondents, respectively, reflecting a higher appreciation of work schedule flexibility during the pandemic compared to the pre-pandemic period.

In the post-pandemic period, flexibility evaluations remained at elevated levels. A score of 9 was once again the most frequently selected, with 41.7% (n=30) of respondents choosing this option. The maximum score of 10 was given by 27.8% (n=20), reflecting a very favorable perception of flexibility.

Table 2. Analysis of Flexibility

Q2	Average	SD
Prepandemic	4.94	1.528
Pandemic	8.85	0.959
Postpandemic	8.93	0.845

Before the pandemic, the average flexibility score was 4.94, indicating a moderate perception of work schedule flexibility. During the pandemic, the average increased significantly to 8.85, reflecting a notable improvement in perceived flexibility. This trend continued after the pandemic, with a slightly higher average of 8.93, suggesting that the positive changes in work schedule management have been sustained and accepted in the long term (Table 2).

The increase in the average flexibility score from 4.94 pre-pandemic to 8.93 post-pandemic indicates a significant shift in employees' perceptions of work schedule flexibility, suggesting that the measures implemented during the pandemic had a lasting positive impact (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Mean Ratings of Flexibility of Work Program

The differences between these means were tested using ANOVA, which indicated statistically significant differences between the means of the studied periods ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3. ANOVA Analysis of Flexibility of Work Program

Q2	ANOVA	
	F	p-value
	282.387	0.000

Levene's test indicated heterogeneous variances between the groups, which led to the application of Dunnett's test for pairwise comparisons between the periods.

Table 4. Levene Test

Q2	Test of Homogeneity of Variances	
	Levene Statistic	p-value
	9.283	0.000

By applying Dunnett's test statistically significant differences were identified between the pre-pandemic period and the other two periods ($p = 0.000$), suggesting an increase in the perception of work schedule flexibility during and after the pandemic. In contrast, no significant differences were found between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.926$), indicating a stabilization of the perceived flexibility of the work schedule. These results suggest that the changes implemented during the pandemic, which were perceived as increasing flexibility, have been maintained and appreciated in the post-pandemic period.

Table 5. Flexibility of Work Program. Pairwise Comparisons of Periods

Q2	Dunnett		p-value
Prepandemic		Pandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.000
Pandemic		Prepandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.926
Postpandemic		Prepandemic	0.000
		Pandemic	0.926

The ANOVA and Dunnett tests confirm that the perception of work schedule flexibility increased significantly during and after the pandemic, highlighting the success of teleworking policies and adaptation to new working conditions.

The results confirm that work schedule flexibility increased significantly during the pandemic (Hypothesis 1.1), indicating an organizational adjustment to remote work models. This highlights the capacity of organizations to rapidly adapt to the circumstances imposed by the pandemic.

An analysis of post-pandemic productivity levels between employees working remotely or in a hybrid model compared to those working on-site at the office reveals significant differences. The average productivity score for employees working remotely or in a hybrid model was 9.05, with a standard deviation of 0.870, while for those working on-site it was 8.53, with a standard deviation of 0.624.

Table 6. Productivity Levels after the Pandemic

		Average	SD
Q2	Hybrid + Home office	9.05	0.870
	Office	8.53	0.624

To assess whether these differences are statistically significant, a t-test was conducted, preceded by Levene's test for equality of variances. Levene's test confirmed that the variances between the two groups were equal ($p = 0.314$), allowing the use of the t-test for equal variances. The t-test results indicated a significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.024$), suggesting that workplace flexibility may positively contribute to employee productivity.

Table 7. Levene's and t-Test

Q2	Levene's Test		t-test	
	F	p-value	t	p-value
Equal variances assumed	1.029	0.314	2.308	0.024
Equal variances not assumed			2.742	0.009

These findings support Hypothesis 1.2, which proposed that the implementation of a flexible work schedule during the pandemic led to an increase in employee productivity at The Company. The statistically significant difference identified through the t-test ($p = 0.024$) indicates that employees working remotely or in a hybrid model reported higher levels of productivity compared to those working on-site. This suggests that flexibility in the workplace not only supported operational continuity during the pandemic but also had a measurable positive impact on employee performance, reinforcing the value of maintaining such flexibility in the post-pandemic work model.

Q3 – Workplace Productivity

Before the pandemic, most respondents (54.2%, $n=39$) rated their workplace productivity at 8, indicating an elevated level of productivity. Scores of 7 and 9, with 18.1% ($n=13$) and 12.5% ($n=9$) respectively, suggest that a considerable proportion of employees were already highly productive even before the pandemic.

During the pandemic, productivity was perceived even more positively, with 41.7% ($n=30$) of respondents giving a score of 9, and 16.7% ($n=12$) assigning the maximum score of 10. This may indicate that the transition to remote work or hybrid arrangements was effective for many employees, allowing them to maintain or even improve their productivity levels.

Post-pandemic productivity evaluations show a continuation of this positive trend, with 56.9% ($n=41$) giving a score of 9 and 15.3% ($n=11$) giving a score of 10. A score of 8 was selected by 19.4% ($n=14$) of respondents. These results suggest that for many employees, workplace efficiency remained high or even improved as organizations continued to adapt to the new working conditions.

The data show that perceived employee productivity increased during the pandemic and remained high post-pandemic, with an average score of 8.75 compared to 7.72 pre-pandemic. This increase may be attributed to improved working conditions, such as greater schedule flexibility and adaptation to remote work, which allowed employees to better manage their time and tasks.

Table 8. Employee Productivity

Q3	Average	SD
Prepandemic	7.72	1.141
Pandemic	8.47	1.126
Postpandemic	8.75	0.931

We evaluated the mean scores on a Likert scale, recording the following average values: 7.72 pre-pandemic, 8.47 during the pandemic, and 8.75 post-pandemic (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Mean Ratings of Employee Productivity

Using ANOVA, we identified significant differences between the groups, indicating statistically relevant variations in perceived productivity ($p < 0.05$).

Table 9. ANOVA Analysis

Q3	ANOVA	
	F	p-value
	17.774	0.000

Due to the results of Levene’s test, which indicated heterogeneous variances between the groups ($p < 0.05$), Dunnett’s test was applied to perform pairwise comparisons between the periods.

Table 10. Levene Tests

Q3	Test of Homogeneity of Variances	
	Levene Statistic	p-value
	3.065	0.049

The results of this test revealed significant differences between the pre-pandemic period and the other two periods ($p = 0.000$ for both comparisons), suggesting a notable improvement in productivity during and after the pandemic compared to the pre-pandemic period. No significant differences were observed between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.291$), indicating a stabilization of productivity levels at an elevated level in the post-pandemic period.

Table 11. Employes Productivity. Comparisons between Periods

	Dunnett		p-value

Q3	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.291
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Pandemic	0.291

Q4 – Communication and Collaboration in the Team and Company

Before the pandemic, most respondents evaluated communication and collaboration as highly effective. A score of 8 was the most frequently selected, with 47.2% (n=34), followed by a score of 9, with 34.7% (n=25). This reflects a positive perception of communication and collaboration before the pandemic, with a 6.9% (n=5) rating as excellent (score 10).

During the pandemic, perceptions of communication and collaboration declined significantly. Lower scores such as 4 and 5 were common, selected by 22.2% (n=16) and 15.3% (n=11), respectively. A mid-level score of 6 was the most frequently selected, with 25% (n=18), suggesting that challenges related to remote work or adapting to new work models had a negative impact on communication and collaboration. Only 6.9% (n=5) rated it as excellent (score 10).

After the pandemic, perceptions of communication and collaboration returned to levels like those before the pandemic. Score 9 became the most frequently selected, with 47.2% (n=34), while score 8 was chosen by 34.7% (n=25). These results indicate a significant improvement and successful adaptation to post-pandemic conditions, due to enhanced communication and collaboration strategies.

Table 12. Means and Standard Deviations in the Periods before, during, and after the Pandemic

Q4	Average	SD
Prepandemic	8.25	1.110
Pandemic	5.11	1.804
Postpandemic	8.44	0.820

Before the pandemic, communication and collaboration within the company were perceived positively, with a mean score of 8.25. During the pandemic, this perception dropped significantly to 5.11, reflecting adaptation difficulties. Post-pandemic, the mean increased to 8.44, indicating a recovery and improvement in communication and collaboration practices due to effective adaptation measures (Table 12). The significant drop in scores during the pandemic, from 8.25 to 5.11, reflects the challenges faced in maintaining effective communication and collaboration under remote work conditions.

The post-pandemic improvement, with a mean of 8.44, suggests that the measures implemented to facilitate communication and collaboration, such as the use of digital technologies, were effective and helped restore communication to levels similar to those before the pandemic (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Mean Ratings of Communication and Collaboration in the Company

The ANOVA test indicated significant differences between the groups ($p < 0.05$), suggesting notable variations in the perception of communication and collaboration across the three periods.

Table 13. ANOVA Analysis of Communication and Collaboration in the Company

		ANOVA	
Q4		F	p-value
		146.511	0.000

Table 14. Levene Test of Communication and Collaboration in the Company

		Test of Homogeneity of Variances	
Q4		Levene Statistic	p-value
		20.125	0.000

Due to the unequal variances confirmed by Levene’s test, Dunnett’s test was applied to perform detailed pairwise comparisons between the periods. The results showed significant differences between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods ($p = 0.000$), indicating a notable decline in the quality of communication and collaboration during the pandemic.

In contrast, no significant differences were found between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.549$), suggesting that communication and collaboration levels returned to pre-pandemic standards.

Table 15. Communication and Collaboration. Pairwise Comparisons of Periods

		Dunnett	p-value
Q4	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.549
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.549
		Pandemic	0.000

In addition, the comparison between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods also revealed significant differences ($p = 0.000$), demonstrating a notable recovery and improvement in communication and collaboration after the pandemic compared to during it.

The significant drop in team communication and collaboration scores from 8.25 before the pandemic to 5.11 during the pandemic confirms the hypothesis (2.1) that the lack of face-to-face interactions had a negative impact on these critical aspects of work.

Q5 – Job Satisfaction

Most respondents were satisfied with their work, with 51.4% ($n=37$) giving a score of 8 and 31.9% ($n=23$) a score of 9. This indicates a high overall level of satisfaction before the disruptions caused by the pandemic. The highest score, 10, was given by 4.2% ($n=3$) of respondents, showing an extremely high degree of satisfaction.

We observe a general trend for improving satisfaction with work, although the distribution of scores has shifted. A score of 9 became the most frequent, given by 45.8% ($n=33$) of participants, and the percentage awarding the maximum score of 10 increased to 11.1% ($n=8$). This suggests that, despite the pandemic's challenges, some employees found ways to improve their job satisfaction, due to increased flexibility in work organization.

After the pandemic, satisfaction with the work performed continued to increase, with 56.9% ($n=41$) of respondents giving a score of 9 and 8.3% ($n=6$) a score of 10. These results reflect successful adaptation to the new working conditions and a continued improvement in work management and task handling.

Table 16. Means and Standard Deviations of Professional Satisfaction in the Periods

		Average	SD
Q5	Prepandemic	8.24	0.847
	Pandemic	8.46	1.020
	Postpandemic	8.64	0.793

The analysis of professional satisfaction across the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic periods shows a slight upward trend in the average scores, from 8.24 pre-pandemic to 8.46 during the pandemic, and up to 8.64 post-pandemic. The slight increase in professional satisfaction from 8.24 pre-pandemic to 8.64 post-pandemic indicates that the company's adaptations in the context of the pandemic had a long-term positive impact on employees' perceptions (Table 16).

Overall professional satisfaction remained stable over time, with no dramatic shift during or after the pandemic (Figure 8). Stability in the central values could suggest that professionals adapted well to the challenges brought by the pandemic, or that institutional support and coping mechanisms were effective. Professional satisfaction proved to be resilient over time, despite major societal disruptions. However, targeted interventions might still be needed for those individuals consistently reporting low satisfaction.

Figure 8. Mean Ratings of Professional Satisfaction

The ANOVA test confirms that there are significant differences between these periods ($p < 0.05$), indicating notable changes in the level of professional satisfaction (Table 17).

Table 17. Professional Satisfaction ANOVA Test

ANOVA			
		F	p-value
Q5		3.683	0.027

The Levene’s Test showed that the variances between groups are not equal, which requires the use of a test that does not assume equality of variances (Table 18).

Table 18. Test of Homogeneity of Variances for Job Satisfaction

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
		Levene Statistic	p-value
Q5		3.471	0.033

The Dunnnett test, used for pairwise group comparisons, indicated that there are no significant differences between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods ($p = 0.400$), nor between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.555$). However, the comparison between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods revealed a significant difference ($p = 0.011$), suggesting a statistically significant improvement in professional satisfaction in the post-pandemic period compared to the pre-pandemic period. The results of the Dunnnett test show that this improvement is statistically significant, highlighting the success of the measures implemented to support employees during and after the global health crisis (Table 19).

Table 19. Job Satisfaction Pairwise Comparisons of Periods

Dunnnett			p-value
Q5	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.400
		Postpandemic	0.011
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.400
		Postpandemic	0.555

	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.011
		Pandemic	0.555

These results indicate that, despite the challenges of the pandemic, the adjustments made by companies to manage this period may be responsible for the long-term improvement in employee satisfaction. The increase in post-pandemic satisfaction may reflect successful adaptation to new working conditions, such as increased flexibility or better management of work-life balance.

Q6 – Stress Level

Stress levels were spread across a wide range of scores, with the most frequent ratings being 5 (41.7%, n=30) and 4 (29.2%, n=21). These data suggest that, before the pandemic, most employees perceived a moderate level of stress at work.

Perceptions of stress intensified for some but remained moderate. Score 5 was the most common, with 48.6% (n=35) indicating a medium level of stress. However, there was an increase in higher scores (8 and 9), reflecting rising stress levels for some employees in the context of the uncertainty and changes brought by the pandemic.

The evaluations indicate a significant decrease in perceived stress, with 68.1% (n=49) of respondents giving a score of 5, suggesting adaptation to the new working conditions or a reduction in stress factors. Higher scores (9) are less frequent but still present, signaling that for some, stress remains a challenge. Although the average stress level increased from 4.65 pre-pandemic to 5.63 post-pandemic, the analysis shows that the adaptations and measures implemented helped manage stress, suggesting that the organization was able to effectively respond to the challenges imposed by the pandemic (Table 20).

Table 20. Means and Standard Deviations of Stress Levels Before the Pandemic

		Average	SD
Q6	Prepandemic	4.65	1.235
	Pandemic	5.03	1.744
	Postpandemic	5.63	1.337

The analysis of workplace stress levels before, during, and after the pandemic indicates an increasing trend in employees' perceived stress across these periods. The average scores on a Likert scale were 4.65 pre-pandemic, 5.03 during the pandemic, and 5.63 post-pandemic.

It is a clear upward trend in scores from pre-pandemic to post-pandemic, indicating a progressive improvement in the perception measured by Stress Levels (Figure 9). The pandemic introduced variability and uncertainty, but the post-pandemic period shows signs of recovery and growth, with higher average satisfaction and less dispersion.

Figure 9. Means and Standard Deviations of Stress Levels before the Pandemic

The ANOVA test confirmed the existence of significant differences between these periods ($p < 0.05$), indicating notable changes in employees' stress levels (Table 21).

Table 21. ANOVA Analysis of Stress Levels

ANOVA			
		F	p-value
Q6		8.173	0.000

Since Levene's test showed that the variances are homogeneous between groups ($p > 0.05$), the Tukey test was applicable for detailed pairwise comparisons between the periods (Table 22).

Table 22. Test of Homogeneity of Stress Levels

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
		Levene Statistic	p-value
Q6		0.771	0.464

The results of the Tukey test show that there is no significant difference between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods ($p = 0.272$), suggesting that initially, the pandemic did not have a significant impact on stress levels. However, the comparison between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods revealed a significant difference ($p = 0.000$), as did the comparison between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.039$), demonstrating that stress levels significantly increased post-pandemic compared to the other two periods.

Thus, hypothesis 3.1 is rejected, as employee stress levels were not significantly higher during the pandemic compared to the other periods. The Tukey test indicates a significant increase in stress levels post-pandemic, which may reflect new challenges and pressures related to the ongoing adjustment to a post-pandemic work environment (Table 23).

Table 23. Tukey Test of Stress Levels

Tukey			p-value
Q6	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.272
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.272

		Postpandemic	0.039
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Pandemic	0.039

These results suggest that, although the pandemic itself did not significantly alter stress levels compared to the pre-pandemic period, the post-pandemic period introduced additional challenges or changes in working conditions that negatively affected employees' well-being.

Q7 – Commitment

Most employees reported feeling highly committed to their company, with 55.6% (n=40) giving a score of 8 and 18.1% (n=13) giving a score of 9. This indicates an elevated level of commitment and a strong connection with the organization, with only 1.4% (n=1) rating their commitment at the maximum level (score 10).

The distribution of scores became wider during the pandemic, indicating greater variability in commitment levels. Score 6, reflecting moderate commitment, was the most frequent at 20.8% (n=15), followed by a score of 8 at 22.2% (n=16) and score 5 at 18.1% (n=13). This shows that the pandemic impacted on employees' sense of commitment, due to the uncertainty and stress caused by changes in the way of working and organizational structure.

As the situation stabilized, employees' commitment to the company appeared to return to levels like those before the pandemic. A significant percentage of 48.6% (n=35) rated their commitment as 8, and 34.7% (n=25) as 9, indicating a return to high commitment and a positive relationship with the organization. Lower scores became less frequent, signaling a general improvement in commitment. The drop in commitment during the pandemic (average of 6.46) and its recovery post-pandemic (average of 8.17) highlight the importance of effective management and support measures in maintaining high employee commitment (Table 24).

Table 24. Means and Standard Deviations of Commitment

		Average	SD
Q7	Prepandemic	7.74	1.126
	Pandemic	6.46	1.635
	Postpandemic	8.17	0.872

Professional commitment was high before the pandemic but experienced a sharp decline during the pandemic, accompanied by increased variability. Postpandemic, commitment fully recovered, reaching a level like the pre-pandemic period and showing greater consistency in respondents' perceptions. This pattern suggests a strong capacity for adaptation and recovery among professionals after a period of crisis (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Analysis of Commitment

The use of the ANOVA test indicated the existence of significant differences between these periods ($p < 0.05$).

Table 25. ANOVA Analysis of Commitment

ANOVA			
		F	p-value
Q7		36.262	0.000

Levene's test showed that the variances between groups are not homogeneous, which required the application of the Dunnett test for detailed pairwise comparisons between the periods.

Table 26. Test of Homogeneity of Commitment Variances

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
		Levene Statistic	p-value
Q7		20.148	0.000

The results of the Dunnett test indicate significant differences between all combinations of the analyzed periods. Compared to the pre-pandemic period, commitment decreased significantly during the pandemic ($p = 0.000$), confirming hypothesis 4.1, but it increased considerably and significantly in the post-pandemic period ($p = 0.000$ compared to the pandemic period and $p = 0.034$ compared to the pre-pandemic period). The Dunnett test confirms the significant differences between the periods, suggesting that the policies implemented post-pandemic were effective in regaining and strengthening employee commitment.

Table 27. Commitment Pairwise Comparisons of Periods

Dunnett			p-value
Q7	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.034
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.034
		Pandemic	0.000

These results suggest that the pandemic had a negative impact on employee commitment, due to increased uncertainty and stress. However, the remarkable recovery of commitment in the post-pandemic period indicates effective adaptation to the new conditions and improved working conditions or supportive measures implemented by the company.

Q8 – Adaptability

The responses indicate good adaptation to changes within the company, with most respondents (45.8%, n=33) giving a score of 8. Additionally, a significant percentage (34.7%, n=25) rated their adaptation as particularly good, with a score of 9. This suggests that, before the pandemic, employees felt comfortable and capable of adapting to organizational changes.

The score distribution became wider during the pandemic but remained high, indicating that many employees managed to adapt effectively even under the difficult conditions imposed by the pandemic. Score 8 remained the most frequent (38.9%, n=28), but there was an increase in extremely high scores (9 and 10), showing that some employees viewed the pandemic as an opportunity to gain experience and grow professionally.

The responses indicate an even better adaptation post-pandemic, with extremely high scores (9 and 10) together totaling 52.1% (n=37). Score 8 also remained frequent, with 42.3% (n=30) of responses, suggesting that most employees felt they had adapted very well to the post-pandemic changes.

The adaptability analysis reflects how employees perceive their ability to adjust to organizational changes throughout the distinct phases of the pandemic. The average scores on a Likert scale were 8.06 in the pre-pandemic period, 7.64 during the pandemic, and 8.55 post-pandemic. The increase in adaptability post-pandemic (average of 8.55) compared to the pre-pandemic period (average of 8.06) indicates that employees managed to improve their capacity to adapt to organizational changes (Table 28).

Table 28. Means and Standard Deviations of Adaptability

		Average	SD
Q8	Prepandemic	8.06	1.060
	Pandemic	7.64	1.541
	Postpandemic	8.55	0.891

The level of adaptability was high and stable before the pandemic. The pandemic caused an increase in variability and a slight decrease in the median, reflecting the challenges and the divergent reactions of individuals to sudden changes. Postpandemic, adaptability returns to a level comparable to the pre-pandemic period, with less variability - a clear sign of resilience and rebalancing among the respondents (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Analysis of Adaptability

The ANOVA test indicates significant differences between these periods ($p < 0.05$), suggesting notable variations in the perception of adaptability (Table 29).

Table 29. ANOVA Analysis for Adaptability

ANOVA		F	p-value
Q8		10.353	0.000

Levene’s test showed that the variances between groups are not homogeneous which is why the Dunnett test was used for pairwise comparisons between the periods (Table 30).

Table 30. Test of Homogeneity of Variances for Adaptability

Test of Homogeneity of Variances		Levene Statistic	p-value
Q8		11.707	0.000

The results of this test show that, although there is no significant difference between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods ($p = 0.171$), the comparison between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods reveals a significant difference ($p = 0.009$), indicating an improvement in adaptability post-pandemic. Similarly, the comparison between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods confirms this trend ($p = 0.000$), suggesting that adaptability was perceived as significantly better post-pandemic compared to during the pandemic.

Table 31. Adaptability Pairwise Comparisons between Periods

Dunnett			p-value
Q8	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.171
		Postpandemic	0.009
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.171
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.009
		Pandemic	0.000

This indicates that organizations were able to learn from the challenges they faced and implement effective strategies that strengthened their employees' adaptability. To test hypothesis 4.2, we analyzed the correlation between management effectiveness and employee adaptability both during the pandemic and afterward.

Table 32. Correlation between Management Efficiency and Employee Adaptability

Correlation		Pearson	p-value
Pandemic	Management Efficiency vs Adaptability	0.287	0.014
Postpandemic	Management Efficiency vs Adaptability	0.335	0.004

The correlation analysis between management effectiveness and adaptability during the pandemic and post-pandemic periods supports the hypothesis that organizations with effective management demonstrate better adaptability to the changes imposed by the pandemic. During the pandemic, the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.287 and the p-value of 0.014 indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between the two variables, suggesting that leadership effectiveness contributed to the organization's ability to adapt to immediate challenges.

This trend strengthens in the post-pandemic period, where the coefficient increases to 0.335 with a p-value of 0.004, reflecting an even stronger connection between effective management and adaptability. These results highlight the crucial role of effective management in navigating pandemic-related uncertainties and in strengthening long-term organizational adaptability.

The correlation analysis shows that effective management significantly contributes to enhancing employee adaptability, both during and after the pandemic.

Q9 – Management Efficiency

Most employees rated management as effective in handling problems, with high scores such as 8 and 10, each selected by 29.2% (n=21). A score of 9 was given by 20.8% (n=15) of respondents, and a score of 7 by 16.7% (n=12). These evaluations reflect a positive perception of the company's management abilities before the pandemic.

The distribution of scores became more dispersed during the pandemic, suggesting that the challenges brought by the pandemic tested management's effectiveness. Mid-range scores, such as 5 and 6, were frequent, each selected by 20.8% (n=15). Higher scores, such as 8 and 9, decreased, and the score of 10 was given by only 6.9% (n=5). This indicates a slight decline in confidence in management's ability to oversee problems under crisis conditions.

The evaluations show a recovery of trust in management effectiveness, with 29.2% (n=21) of employees giving scores of 9 and 10, indicating a high appreciation of management's abilities post-pandemic. Score 8, also considered high, was selected by 33.3% (n=24), showing a general improvement compared to the pandemic period.

The analysis of management efficiency over the studied period reveals that the perceived effectiveness of management decreased during the pandemic (average of 6.89) and recovered post-pandemic (average of 8.79), highlighting the challenges faced by management during the crisis and the success of the measures implemented to improve this perception post-pandemic (Table 33).

Table 33. Means and Standard Deviations of Management Efficiency

		Average	SD
Q9	Prepandemic	8.51	1.267
	Pandemic	6.89	1.658
	Postpandemic	8.79	0.963

Before the pandemic, management efficiency was perceived as high, consistent, and stable. During the pandemic, perceptions deteriorated significantly, becoming polarized - some maintained their trust, while others experienced what they felt was poor management (SD = 1.658). After the pandemic, perceptions of managerial efficiency not only recovered but surpassed pre-pandemic levels, suggesting

a sustainable management approach that adapted, learned from the crisis, and led to improved leadership practices (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Analysis of Management Efficiency

The ANOVA test confirmed significant differences between these periods ($p < 0.05$) (Table 34).

Table 34. ANOVA Analysis for Management Efficiency

ANOVA		
	F	p-value
Q9	43.205	0.000

Due to the results of Levene’s test, which indicated non-homogeneous variances between groups (Table 35), the Dunnett test was used for pairwise comparisons between the periods.

Table 35. Test of Homogeneity of Variances for Adaptability

Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
	Levene Statistic	p-value
Q9	12.294	0.000

The results of this test show significant differences between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods ($p = 0.000$), indicating a significant decline in perceived management efficiency during the pandemic. In comparison, there are no significant differences between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods ($p = 0.365$), suggesting that management efficiency returned to pre-pandemic levels. Additionally, the comparison between the pandemic and post-pandemic periods shows a significant improvement in management efficiency post-pandemic ($p = 0.000$) (Table 36).

Table 36. Management Efficiency Pairwise Comparisons between Periods

Dunnett			p-value
Q9	Prepandemic	Pandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.365
	Pandemic	Prepandemic	0.000
		Postpandemic	0.000
	Postpandemic	Prepandemic	0.365
		Pandemic	0.000

The Dunnett test indicates a significant recovery in management efficiency post-pandemic, reflecting the organization's effective strategic and operational adjustments.

These results suggest that the pandemic placed considerable pressure on management, temporarily affecting its efficiency. However, the recovery in the post-pandemic period suggests that the measures implemented to counter the negative effects of the pandemic were effective, restoring and even surpassing the management efficiency observed before the pandemic. This recovery may reflect the strategic and operational adjustments made to better respond to employee needs and market challenges in a post-crisis environment.

5. Conclusions

The present study offers a comprehensive analysis of the managerial impacts, operational adjustments, and employee outcomes associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, using The Company as a case study. The findings highlight significant organizational shifts in work structures, communication practices, leadership dynamics, and employee well-being, all of which have critical implications for future organizational development and resilience strategies.

The pandemic triggered a change in thinking in how work is organized, with teleworking evolving from a marginal practice to a mainstream operational model. This transformation required rapid technological adoption, significant process adjustments, and cultural change. The transition was not without challenges, including cybersecurity threats, communication disruptions, and coordination difficulties. However, the findings confirm that these barriers were overcome through strategic investments in digital infrastructure and adaptive leadership practices. Employees reported higher levels of perceived work schedule flexibility and productivity during and after the pandemic, reflecting the effectiveness of the transition to more flexible work arrangements. The statistically significant increase in these metrics underscores the long-term viability and benefits of hybrid and remote work models when implemented with appropriate managerial support.

Communication and collaboration initially suffered during the transition to remote work, reflecting the difficulties of maintaining team cohesion and information flow without face-to-face interactions. Nevertheless, the post-pandemic data reveals a full recovery to pre-pandemic levels, supported by the strategic use of collaborative technologies and renewed management focus on building team trust and accountability. This highlights the adaptive capacity of organizations to redesign communication channels and rebuild team dynamics in response to environmental disruptions.

Employee satisfaction showed a stable or slightly improving trend across the studied period, suggesting that organizational adjustments, particularly the move toward more flexible work arrangements, had a positive effect on the overall work experience. However, an increase in reported stress levels post-pandemic signals the emergence of new or persisting challenges in work-life balance, workload management, or personal well-being. This underscores the need for organizations to continue investing in mental health support, workload optimization, and employee well-being programs to ensure sustainable performance and retention.

Notably, employee commitment, which declined during the pandemic, showed a remarkable recovery post-pandemic, exceeding pre-pandemic levels. This suggests that the organization's efforts to rebuild trust, provide support, and communicate transparently were successful in re-engaging the workforce. Similarly, employee adaptability increased significantly post-pandemic, demonstrating the workforce's capacity to embrace change when supported by effective management. The positive correlations identified between management effectiveness and employee adaptability reinforce the critical role of leadership in navigating organizational change and building resilience.

Management effectiveness itself experienced a temporary decline during the pandemic, reflecting the unprecedented complexity of the crisis. However, the subsequent recovery to pre-pandemic levels—and even slight improvements—indicate that the organization successfully learned from the challenges faced. This learning translated into refined strategies, enhanced crisis management capabilities, and a more resilient leadership culture.

From a financial and operational perspective, the pandemic exposed vulnerabilities in supply chains, cash flow management, and workforce stability. The Company's experience demonstrates that organizations capable of implementing diversified financing strategies, strengthening financial management, and leveraging government support programs are better positioned to weather such crises. Additionally, the forced acceleration of digital transformation not only ensured operational continuity but also positioned the organization for future growth in an increasingly digital economy.

In summary, the study confirms that while the COVID-19 pandemic posed significant managerial, operational, and human capital challenges, it also served as a catalyst for lasting positive transformation. The findings validate the strategic importance of flexibility, digital capability, employee-centered leadership, and initiative-taking change management. For organizations aiming to thrive in future volatile environments, these elements should remain central to their strategic agendas. Strengthening resilience is no longer optional but a critical competence for sustainable organizational success. The experience of The Company provides valuable insights for other organizations seeking to leverage crisis-induced changes as opportunities for long-term growth and employee engagement.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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